

Diethylammonium Molybdates and Tungstates

M. R. UDUPA* and M. N. HOLLA

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras-600036

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The interaction of molybdic oxide and ammonium paratungstate with diethylamine resulted in the isolation of diethylammonium trimolybdate and tritungstate. Passing hydrogen sulphide to the aqueous solutions of diethylammonium molybdate and tungstate, the respective tetrathiomolybdate and tetrathiotungstate are crystallized out. The compounds are characterized by X-ray powder photography, electronic and infrared spectral measurements and thermogravimetric analysis.

EXTENSIVE studies have been made^{1,2} on alkali metal chalcogenomolybdates and chalcogenotungstates. As a part of general investigation on the stabilization of bulky complex anions with non-spherical counter cations such as morpholinium³, hexamethylene-tetrammonium⁴, piperidinium and pyrrolidinium⁵, various thiometallates have been characterized. In this paper are reported the results of the studies made on trimolybdate, tritungstate, tetrathiomolybdate and tetrathiotungstates of diethylammonium, (DEA). The compounds are isolated and examined by ultra-violet, visible and infrared spectral measurements, X-ray powder patterns and thermal behaviour.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are commercially available pure reagent grade.

Preparation

Diethylammonium trimolybdate $(DEA)_2Mo_3O_{10}$ was prepared by adding in portions about 4g of molybdic oxide to a constantly stirring 12ml 50% aqueous diethylamine. The contents are warmed, if necessary and filtered to remove the suspended particles, if any. The clear solution was kept aside for 3-4 days. The crystallized solid was collected on a filter, washed with acetone and air-dried. Found, N 4.84, Mo 47.64%; Calcd. for $[(C_2H_5)_2NH_2]^+ [Mo_3O_{10}]^{2-}$, N 4.70, Mo 48.30%.

Diethylammonium tritungstate, $(DEA)_2W_3O_{10}$ was prepared by adding about 3ml diethylamine to an aqueous solution containing 2g of ammonium paratungstate. The solution was boiled till all the ammonia was driven off and was kept aside for 2-3 days, when colourless crystalline product separated out. The solid was filtered, washed with acetone and air-dried. Found, N 3.41, W 63.44%; Calcd. for $[(C_2H_5)_2NH_2]^+ [W_3O_{10}]^{2-}$, N 3.26, W 64.15%.

Diethylammonium tetrathiomolybdate, $(DEA)_2MoS_4$ was prepared by passing hydrogen sulphide to a solution containing 1.5g of MoO_3 in about 5ml 50% aqueous diethylamine. The red crystals separated were

collected on a filter, washed with small amount of acetone and air-dried. Found, N 7.41, S 34.11, Mo 25.91%; Calcd for $[(C_2H_5)_2NH_2]^+ [MoS_4]^{2-}$, N 6.08, S 27.84, W 39.94%.

Diethylammonium tetrathiotungstate, $(DEA)_2WS_4$, was prepared by the same method as that of $(DEA)_2MoS_4$, by passing hydrogen sulphide to a diethylammonium tungstate solution. The separated golden yellow crystals were filtered, washed with acetone and air-dried. Found, N 6.22, S 27.71, W 40.43%; calcd. for $[(C_2H_5)_2NH_2]^+ [WS_4]^{2-}$, N 6.08, S 27.84, W 39.94%.

Physical measurements

The X-ray diffraction photographs were taken using a Debye-Scherrer powder camera of diameter 114.6 mm and $CuK\alpha$ radiation. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR 12 spectrometer employing both nujol mull and KBr pellet techniques. The ultra-violet and visible spectra were measured using Carl Zeiss DMR 21 recording spectrometer. The thermogravimetric studies were made in air using a recording Stanton thermobalance at a linear heating rate of 6° per min. About 200 mg samples were taken in mullite crucible container for each run.

Results and Discussion

Trimolybdate and tritungstate: The trimolybdate and the tritungstate are readily soluble in water; in acid medium the respective metal trioxides are precipitated out. The X-ray powder patterns of the trimetallates and the tetrathiometallates are given in Table 1. The d_{hkl} values indicate that the trimolybdate and the tritungstate are not isostructural. The absence of isomorphism is also noticed⁶⁻⁸ in potassium trimetallates, $K_2M_3O_{10}$ and potassium tetrametallates, $K_2M_4O_{13}$ ($M=MO, W$), among which the structures of the tetrametallates are thoroughly investigated. The tetramolybdate is made up⁶ of infinite chains of edge sharing distorted MoO_6 octahedra whereas the analogues tetratungstate consists^{9,10} of six membered rings of cornered linked WO_6 octahedra.

* Senior author.

TABLE 1—X-RAY POWDER PATTERNS (A) OF DIETHYLAMMONIUM METALLATES

(DEA) ₂ Mo ₃ O ₁₀	(DEA) ₂ W ₃ O ₁₀	(DEA) ₂ MoS ₄	(DEA) ₂ WS ₄
3.72s	3.90m	8.04s	8.10s
2.93m	3.38m	7.44s	7.48s
2.77s	3.23s	5.32m	5.40s
2.44m	2.84w	4.21m	4.23s
2.28s	2.70s	4.07m	4.06m
2.21s	2.59m	3.80m	3.83m
1.90w	2.25m	3.65w	3.65m
1.84w	1.92w	3.41m	3.40m
1.74w	1.83w	3.09w	3.12w
1.69w	1.71w	2.71w	2.72w
1.60w	1.63w		

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak

TABLE 2—METAL-OXYGEN STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹) OF TRIMETALLATES

(DEA) ₂ Mo ₃ O ₁₀ : 950sh,	925s,	905s,	895s,	850w,	785m,	720m,	642s,	500s,b,	410m
(DEA) ₂ W ₃ O ₁₀ : 930s,b,	900s,	850s,	800s,b,	700s,	500m,	345			

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, sh=shoulder.

The i. r. spectral frequencies due to metal-oxygen stretching are given in Table 2. Gatehouse and Leverett⁶ and Caillet and Saumagne⁹ have studied the usefulness of i. r. spectral data to find out Mo-O coordination in the molybdates. The appearance of Mo-O stretching frequency around 830 cm⁻¹ suggests MoO₄ tetrahedral coordination¹⁰, several multiple bands in the region 850-960 cm⁻¹ indicates edge sharing MoO₆ octahedra and 2-3 strong bands in the region 850-950 cm⁻¹ suggests edge sharing MoO₆ octahedra and MoO₆ square pyramids⁶. The Mo-O stretching frequencies observed in (DEA)₂Mo₃O₁₀ resemble those of potassium trimolybdate which suggests that it has similar type of Mo-O bonding⁶ as in K₂Mo₃O₁₀.

The thermal behaviour characteristics of the trimolybdate and the tritungstate are quite identical. The compounds start decomposing around 140° and the final residues obtained at 450°, on chemical and X-ray analyses, are found to be the respective metal trioxides. The weight loss observed for the trimolybdate was 28% and that for the tritungstate 19%; the corresponding calculated values for the formation of metal trioxides are 27.6 and 19.1% respectively.

Tetrathiomolybdate and tetrathiotungstate : The tetrathio-salts are highly soluble in water and on acidification of the solution the respective metal trisulphides are precipitated out. The salts give out slowly hydrogen sulphide and the amine with time, resulting in the formation of metal trisulphides. The d-spacings of the thiosalts (Table 1) suggest that diethylammonium tetrathiomolybdate and tetrathiotungstate are isostructural as observed in the case of alkali metal and ammonium tetrathiometallates^{1,1,1,2}.

The electronic spectral frequencies together with the molar absorption are tabulated in Table 3. The spectra showed three characteristic frequencies with the molar absorptivity of the order 10⁴. The electronic transitions are assigned to t₁→2e(ν₁), t₁→4t₂(ν₂) and 3t₂→2e(ν₃) according to Viste-Gray M. O. scheme¹³. The infrared spectra of the tetrathiosalts exhibit¹⁴ triply degenerate i. r. active bands due to metal-sulphur vibrations in the region 450-500 cm⁻¹. The present compounds showed bands around 470 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to M-S stretching vibrations.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC AND I. R. SPECTRAL FREQUENCIES OF TETRATHIOMETALLATES

Compound	Electronic (ε=1 × 10 ⁻⁴) (nm)			Infrared (cm ⁻¹)
	ν ₁	ν ₂	ν ₃	
(DEA) ₂ MoS ₄	466 (1.12)	315 (1.81)	240 (2.85)	495sh, 470s
(DEA) ₂ WS ₄	390 (1.18)	275 (2.73)	214 (3.52)	466s

s=strong, sh=shoulder.

The thermal behaviour of the diethylammonium tetrathiosalts are similar to that of the corresponding ammonium tetrathiosalts^{15,16} in the sense that they decompose to give the respective metal trioxides through the formation of metal trisulphides, as the intermediate products. The salts start decomposing around 120° and the weight loss was rapid upto 250°. Around 300° the weight loss curves indicate the formation of metal trisulphides. The weight loss observed for the tetrathiomolybdate was 49% and that for the tetrathiotungstate 39%. The calculated values for the formation of MoS₃ and WS₃ are 48.4 and 39.2% respectively. The final products of decomposition obtained at 500° are found on X-ray and chemical analyses to be MoO₃ and WO₃. The thermograms showed the weight loss at 500°, for the tetrathiomolybdate was 61% and that for the tetrathiotungstate was 50%. The calculated weight losses for the two salts are 61.4 and 49.6% respectively. From the thermogravimetric results the decomposition scheme of the tetrathiosalts can be given as

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